

MAPWORMS

Mimicking Adaptation
and Plasticity in
WORMS

D1.11 RP3 UPDATE OF THE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable reports the final version of the MAPWORMS Data Management Plan (DMP) submitted at month 48 (M48). This document represents the final update of the DMP, which has been maintained as a living document and revised throughout the project lifecycle in line with the progress achieved.

The MAPWORMS Data Management Plan (DMP) defines the management steps and protocols that inform and guide the researchers involved in the project for properly managing their data and software. The MAPWORMS Team recognizes the importance of effective data management of research data and the development of a robust DMP in anticipation of planned research activities. Following the Horizon 2020 FAIR DMP Template,^[1] the MAPWORMS DMP provides information about the handling, collection, processing, and generation of research data, as well as the applied methodologies and standards, the procedures of data sharing and open access, and the curation and preservation of the data after the end of the project.

In this final version, the main updates include the following:

- ✓ *A table is accompanying each data category showing the repositories where the data outcomes are stored. This mainly refers to the Biological Data as for this kind of data domain-specific repositories instead of just a generic one (e.g. Zenodo) were selected to enhance findability and reusability of data.*
- ✓ *A consolidated table summarizing all outcomes e.g., datasets, scans, maps etc produced throughout the project's duration and the repositories in which they are deposited (see Figure 9 and ANNEX VII). This table enables any interested user (scientist, student, researchers etc) to easily navigate and identify the project's openly available data, in line with the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability).*
- ✓ *An update of the MAPWORMS community in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/mapworms/>) is performed. It is noted that our Zenodo community was created since the beginning of the project to store all project's outcomes; this is certified as Part of the EU Open Research Repository.*
- ✓ *The list of deliverables and their dissemination level (sensitive, or public) is checked and finalised (Table 13).*

1 INTRODUCTION

MAPWORMS project aims to design robots that are inspired by simplified forms of marine Annelida, able to perform tasks in response to environmental stimuli, thus adapting to the working environment with a shape-morphing strategy. Specifically, this project, intends to: 1) study the adaptation and plasticity of the marine Annelids body; 2) develop a mathematical model of Annelida plasticity and adaptation to the environment; 3) develop smart soft materials embodying responsiveness, shape morphing, and self-healing capabilities; 4) develop bio-inspired modular shape morphing robots across scales.

As it is stated in the Description of Action (DoA) and specifically in Task 1.3, this DMP is a reference document for the Consortium, and it outlines how the research data collected or generated within the project activities were handled during the project and will remain in force after the end of the project. For this reason, the MAPWORMS DMP was considered as a living document that was revised in accordance with the project achievements.

Since data gathering and curation are key factors, a Data Manager (DM) was appointed for the DMP handling during the MAPWORMS kick-off meeting, on the 13th of May 2022, in Pisa (Italy). Figure 1 presents the organizational structure of the MAPWORMS DMP. Throughout the duration of the project the DM defined the framework of data handling to inform and guide all participating partners in properly managing their data and software. The DM was in contact with all partners – individually and as a group – throughout the project life in order to discuss and solve any possible difficulties in data sharing and publishing. In addition, the DM worked closely with the Innovation Manager (IM) and the Innovation Management Board (IMB) for the appropriate handling of data and in particular of those related to the project results patenting, which is considered sensitive data.

Figure 1 Organizational structure of the MAPWORMS Data Management Plan

This document is the final version of the MAPWORMS DMP and is related to all six Work Packages and in particular: WP1 Project coordination, dissemination, and communication, WP2 Ecological, taxonomical and morphological studies for selected species of marine Annelida, WP3 Annelid shape-morphing modelling, WP4 Smart stimuli-responsive hydrogels, WP5 Morphing robots across scales and WP6 Robots testing towards application case studies and exploitation activities.

1.1 ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION

Grant Agreement number: 101046846

Project title: Mimicking Adaptation and Plasticity in WORMS

Project acronym: MAPWORMS

Call: HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN-01

Topic: HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN-01-01

Type of action: HORIZON-EIC

Service: EISMEA/E/01 Project

Starting date: May 01, 2022

Project duration: 48 months

Data Management Plan Responsible: HCMR

1.2 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN SCHEDULE

Several Data Management Team meetings among the different partners were organised throughout the project duration, where the data delivery and standardisations were discussed and finalised. The timeline of the evolution of the DMP is illustrated in Figure 2. This is the final update of the DMP (DMP v.3) in the framework of the third reporting period which outlines how the research data collected or generated within the project activities have been handled during the project and will remain in force after the end of the project. All relevant tasks have been completed, and the DMP has been updated according to the project's final results.

Figure 2 DMP timeline

2 DATA SUMMARY

MAPWORMS data has been used to develop bio-inspired robots able to perform tasks in response to environmental stimuli. Specifically, data generated and collected within WP2 are related to annelid taxonomy, behavior, and ecology providing the biological background for WPs 3, 4 and 5. Furthermore, data derived from WP3 developed theoretical and numerical tools for worm and robot modeling. Data generated by WP4 are related to the development and characterization of stimuli-responsive hydrogels that exhibit controlled stiffness functions, shape-memory, and self-healing properties. The aforementioned data have been used in WP5 in order to develop a worm-inspired soft modular robot featured by shape morphing capabilities and responsiveness to environmental stimuli. Selected data have been used for WP6 in order to investigate potential applications and exploitation opportunities of the robot.

In the present document, the term 'data' refers to the following four main categories of information that have been used and/or produced during the project. These are:

- 1. Biological Data:** data collected through the processes described in WP2. This data category provides the solid biological background for WP3, WP4 and WP5, by using Annelida Phylum and its evolutionary patterns as a model and source of bioinspiration.

2. **Technical Data:** all data related to WP3, WP4 and WP5 and partly WP6. In particular, the processes of Annelid shape-morphing modelling, stimuli-responsive materials and morphing robot design and characterization, as well as testing in advanced platforms for applications under analysis.

3. **Patent-search Data:** related to WP6, giving an overview of already available technologies that are patented in the field of research using methodology developed within the project.

4. **Dissemination Data:** information released during the MAPWORMS project through social media and its official website, as well as the scientific publications referring to the procedures and/or the results of the research conducted.

Table 1 presents a summary of the research domains and the data, software, and data file types that have been used and produced by the participating partners of the MAPWORMS project. The overall information was provided from the answers given by the MAPWORMS partners when replying to the MAPWORMS Data Management Questionnaire (see ANNEX II), which was based on the questions of the Horizon 2020 FAIR Data Management Plan Template.^[1]

This Questionnaire was sent to each partner on May 20th 2022, along with instructions, in order to collect information on the data they are going to collect and/or produce during the project and on potential preferences for handling their data. Furthermore, Table 1 was updated based on the outcomes discussed during the Final meeting held in Pontedera (Italy), in March 2026.

Table 1 The research domains, the data formats and data files that are produced by the participating partners of the MAPWORMS project.

Partner Contribution	Data Category	Data type	Research domain(s)	Data standards/ vocabularies and software/ tools used	Data file types
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Distributional/ Georeferenced data	biogeographic research, traits, taxonomy	Darwin Core standards, OBIS-ENV-DATA IPT (integrated publishing tool) (open source)	csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx, .txt; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods; .xml; .rtf; .txt; .html; .doc; .docx; JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg), TIFF (.tif, .tiff)
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Genomic data	DNA sequencing	M2B3 Reporting Standard Read data: general (CRAM, BAM, Fastq) and platform specific (SFF, PacBio, Oxford Nanopore, CompleteGenomics) Assembled and annotated sequence data: flat file format (FASTA, XML), Multiple Sequence Alignment (MSA) formats	csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx, .txt; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods; SPSS, Stata, Sas, DDI XML, .sav; .dta; xml; .rtf; .txt; .html; .doc; .docx; .fas

CoNISMa	Biological Data	Morphological data	measurements, pictures, drawings		csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx, .txt; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods; JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg), TIFF (.tif, .tiff),
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Behavioral data	videos, footages, ethograms		csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx, .txt; doc; .docx; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods; MPEG-4 (.mp4), motion JPEG 2000 (.mj2)), AVI (.avi)
HCMR	Biological Data	Micro-CT data	Micro-CT images, digital images, videos	microCTvlab, Slice-Drop (open source) CTVox, nRecon (commercial)	JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg), TIFF (.tif, .tiff), PNG (.png); MPEG-4 (.mp4), AVI (.avi); nifti (.nii)
HCMR	Biological Data	Morphological data	2D/3D analysis	CTAn and DataViewer softwares (commercial), Dragonfly software (Free license for researchers with non-commercial activities/Commercial) Landmark (freeware)	csv; .xls; .xlsx, .txt, .obj; .stl
SSSA	Technical Data	Modelling data	numbers, codes, software, mechanical simulations, images, movies, datasheets	MATLAB (academic version), Solidworks (academic version), COMSOL (for a fee)	Datasheet (.csv, .xls, .xlsx, .txt); MATLAB (.m, .fig); Multiphysics (.mph); CAD (.stl); Drawings (.eps, .svg); JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg); PNG (.png); MPEG-4 (.mp4), AVI (.avi); pdf
VEXLUM	Technical Data	Laser characterization data	Datasheets	Power, wavelength, beam quality, 2D drawings	.pdf
HUJI	Technical Data	Experimental data	synthesis and characterisation of stimuli-responsive hydrogels	Origin software ImageJ	xls; xlx; JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg), TIFF (.tif, .tiff), PNG (.png); .opj, .opju
SSSA	Technical Data	Morphing data	numbers, codes, software, mechanical	MATLAB (academic version), Arduino (open source) LabView (for a fee),	Datasheet (.csv, .xls, .xlsx, .txt); MATLAB (.m, .fig); Multiphysics (.Mph);

			simulations, images, movies	Solidworks (academic version), COMSOL (for a fee), Instron (commercial), ImageJ (open source), Vibrating Sample Magnetometer (commercial), Force sensors (commercial), Tracker (open source)	CAD(.stl); Drawings (.eps, .svg); JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg); PNG (.png); MPEG-4 (.mp4), AVI (.avi); pdf
ACMIT	Technical Data	Anatomical modelling data	anatomical models (phantoms)	medical ontologies (such as SNOMED CT or OntoSPM), CAD software (Solidworks, Fusion), 3D Slicer (open source), Prusaslicer (open source)	docx, xlsx, txt, pdf, png, jpeg, stl, 3mf, gcode, step, f3d, sldprt, sldasm, nrrd, mml
ACMIT	Patent-search Data	patent lists	Soft robots for medical technology	Google Patent, Espacenet, Patoffice	pdf, xlsx, docx
All	Dissemination Data		presentation, article, 3D models for touchscreen monitor, micro-CT images and videos for mobile app etc.	D1.2_project handbook, project Grant Agreement Drishti and Drishti Prayog (open source)	JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg, .tif, .tiff), PNG (.png); txt, .doc; .docx; pdf; html; MPEG-4 (.mp4), AVI (.avi); xml, .drishtiprayog (.avi); xml, .drishtiprayog

DATA RE-USE

Concerning the reuse of existing data, **CoNISMa** examined published literature on annelids along the Salento peninsula to extract historical distributional data. Furthermore, regarding molecular analyses and phylogenetic reconstructions, sequences deposited in online repositories were used to compare with the newly obtained ones. **HCMR** examined the protocols and methods of annelids micro-CT scans created by the HCMR imaging laboratory, in order to guide the development of the new micro-CT methods for the MAPWORMS project. Additionally, new scanning protocols have been created as the selected species needed different preparation and scanning parameters. For **SSSA** and **VEXLUM**, no existing data were used as the data produced are strictly connected to the used hardware and laser systems. Accordingly, both SSSA and VEXLUM relied on their background knowledge and expertise in soft robotics and laser systems to support the development of the project's new results. **HUJI** applied existing knowledge and experience of the laboratory to design the hydrogels. The pre-existing methods guided the development of new gel materials. For **ACMIT**, based on material and robot development and the identified clinical application, existing anatomical data (e.g. [NasalSeg](#) and [cgtrader](#)) and material data were used for the generation of the test models.

DATA SIZE & UTILITY

The size of the MAPWORMS data varies, from few MB (e.g., distributional data, images, videos) to several GB (e.g., micro-CT datasets). Specifically, 81 micro-CT scans have been generated with a total size of 2.43 TB. Each micro-CT dataset available for download in the MicroCTvlab (<https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/mapworms>) is approximately 200-350 MB.

Concerning data utility, researchers from several disciplines will be interested. Species distributional data derived by **CoNISMa** have provided updated biodiversity checklists of annelids in Italian Seas for the Scientific Committee for the Fauna of Italy and for Marine Protected Areas (e.g., Marine Protected Area of Porto Cesareo, Marine Protected Area of Torre Guaceto) and the Apulia Region as required by Italian and European Directives. Molecular data will be useful for building DNA barcode libraries for environmental DNA metabarcoding purposes. Morphological and behavioral data were used for MAPWORMS researchers for the development of the annelids modelling. All the aforementioned data will be also useful for annelids taxonomists and ecologists outside the consortium. For this reason, a consolidated table is provided in ANNEX VII, indicating the repositories in which the project's datasets are deposited, in order to facilitate data discovery and reuse by interested users.

Despite the taxonomical and ecological interest, the micro-CT data produced by **HCMR** can be used by academics and students for educational and research purposes, artists and animators for artistic purposes or experts in micro-CT technology for the investigation of digitization protocols and methods. Data derived by **HUJI** and **SSSA** will be of broad interest in diverse scientific disciplines, including chemistry, drug-delivery, catalysis, sensing, actuation, materials science, robotics, and micro/nanoparticle systems. Additionally, **VELLUM**'s laser system with improved system performance, compact modular design and higher efficiency, could be of interest to the developers of medical technology or other application fields.

ACMIT data and, in particular, patent-search data, remain closed as are considered sensitive. Nevertheless, a short summary of the Intellectual Property handling as well as further exploitation of project results is included in deliverable D1.16 – Updated dissemination, communication and exploitation plan which will be publicly available through the MAPWORMS community in Zenodo when finalised.

2.1 BIOLOGICAL DATA

2.1.1. INTRODUCTION

The crucial first step for the successful output of the MAPWORMS project was related to the taxonomy, behavior, and ecology of Annelida. A dedicated WP, in particular the WP2 – Ecological, taxonomical and morphological studies for selected species of marine Annelida

aimed to provide a solid biological background for WP3, WP4 and WP5. Specifically, CoNISMa and HCMR performed behavioral, ecological, taxonomical, morphological, and anatomical studies aimed at characterizing the identity, ecological and biological traits of Annelida species.

The result of this WP was the generation of five different types of data which belong to the general category of Biological Data (Table 1):

- a. Distributional/ georeferenced data
- b. Genomic data
- c. Morphological data and Behavioral data
- d. Micro CT data

A. DISTRIBUTIONAL/ GEOREFERENCED DATA

CoNISMa has submitted metadata and data from the sampling campaigns to OBIS and in particular to its dedicated node for the Mediterranean Region, which is MedOBIS (<http://medobis.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/>). MedOBIS hosts standardized and quality controlled marine data for the Mediterranean Sea from a wide range of references and time periods, and it is encompassed within the framework of OBIS Nodes. It is hosted by the Institute of Marine Biology, Biotechnology and Aquaculture (IMBBC, <https://imbbs.hcmr.gr/>) of the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR, <https://www.hcmr.gr/en/>). Since EMODNET (<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en>) and LifeWatchGreece (<https://www.lifewatchgreece.eu/>) projects, MedOBIS started operating as a Tier 2 Node. The main principle of MedOBIS is the contribution to science with FAIR and OPEN data. All the data are published through an Integrated Publishing Toolkit (IPT), <http://ipt.medobis.eu/>, harvested by OBIS and GBIF. The IPT provides the ability to assign DOIs to datasets by using a DataCite account, creating a data repository. The IPT is an open-source software tool, freely available by the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) network.

For distributional/ georeferenced data, a metadata template accompanied every sampling event, in order to collect as much information as possible while being in the field. This metadata template is presented in ANNEX III. The relevant data were sent to the MedOBIS Data Management Team in HCMR to be standardized, quality controlled and finally published to the MedOBIS Repository, under CC-BY License (see Table 2).

The Salento Peninsula has been selected as the source of the biological material collected due to its geographical position and environmental variability, which offers a wide array of potential model species within a relatively restricted area. Information about the marine annelid fauna occurring along the Salento Peninsula coastline (Italy) was obtained by two sources: a) from data mining the available literature, focusing on papers dealing with

community ecology and annelid taxonomy, and b) from new sampling events. It is worth mentioning that a recent publication from CoNISMA^[2] confirmed the importance of the Salento Peninsula as a marine biodiversity hotspot and stressed the need for further detailed research on marine annelids even in the relatively well-known Mediterranean Sea.

The outcome of data mining was two separate datasets, one with georeferenced records of annelid species and one including non-georeferenced literature reporting annelid species along the Salento Peninsula. Both datasets were standardized based on Darwin Core Standards and along with their metadata are available through MedOBIS repository (see Table 2). See ANNEX V for more details on Darwin Core standards used. The literature datasets were also uploaded into MAPWORMS Zenodo community, without any access restrictions.

During the first year of the MAPWORMS project (between 01/05/2022 and 28/02/2023), approximately 40 sampling events were performed in different habitats and at different depths to obtain new distributional data about marine annelids along the Salento Peninsula. The dataset of new annelid occurrences also followed the Darwin Core standardization process, and its metadata are available through MedOBIS repository. The dataset was uploaded into MAPWORMS Zenodo community and remained under embargoed period until April 30, 2025, but now is freely open to any interest user.

The gathered georeferenced distributional data allowed for the reconstruct a distributional map of marine annelids along the coasts of Salento, highlighting in particular the occurrence of well-studied and scarcely studied areas and marine systems. This map, along with interesting taxonomic and statistical biological information, is available through MAPWORMS Zenodo community.

The following table summarizes all three datasets produced by CoNISMa and indicates the open repositories through which the data are available and accessible. Notably, the first step undertaken by the MAPWORMS data manager consisted of collecting the datasets and uploading them to Zenodo. Subsequently, a second and final step focused on the dedicated curation of provided data, including coordinate precision assessment, taxonomic verification, and Darwin Core standardization, prior to their publication in major aggregators such as OBIS and GBIF. Additionally, the following table presents the relevant deliverables and publications.

Table 2 Distributional and georeferenced data outputs and their repositories.

Partner Contribution	Data Category	Data type	Title	DOI	Repository submitted	Relevant link
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Distributional/ Georeferenced data, Dataset	Georeferenced literature records of annelid species along the Salento Peninsula from 1975 to 2023	https://doi.org/10.15468/xd78ew	a. Zenodo b. MedOBIS c. OBIS d. GBIF	a. https://zenodo.org/records/7869994 b. https://ipt.medobis.eu/resource?r=georeferenced-literature-annelids-salento-peninsula

						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> c. https://obis.org/dataset/68f01f07-36bc-46b9-a57e-ded03db39788 d. https://www.gbif.org/en/dataset/8e6479b6-fb16-493f-8fd6-50f89da374e9
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Distributional data, Dataset	Literature records of annelid species along the Salento Peninsula without georeferenced, 1968-2020	https://doi.org/10.15468/3zz2pj	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Zenodo b. MedOBIS c. OBIS d. GBIF 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. https://zenodo.org/records/7869960 b. https://ipt.medobis.eu/resource?r=annelid_salento c. https://obis.org/dataset/8f98c26e-8588-484c-86d6-af2860ae87a0 d. https://www.gbif.org/dataset/a47ab2e1-d507-468b-23f-e1cda7739eae
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Distributional/ Georeferenced data, Dataset	New records of annelid species along the Salento Peninsula	https://doi.org/10.25607/zauiw2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Zenodo b. MedOBIS c. OBIS d. GBIF 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. https://zenodo.org/records/7870065 b. https://ipt.medobis.eu/resource?r=new_records_annelid_salento c. https://obis.org/dataset/4067c146-d621-4c27-add2-63f85d46109d d. https://www.gbif.org/dataset/77c9cc6c-1c4e-4b08-806d-a95cc4b5829e
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Distributional/ Georeferenced data, Deliverable	D2.1 Georeferenced Annelida distribution map along the Apulia coast	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8039801	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/8039801
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Distributional/ Georeferenced data, poster	Towards a new standard for marine annelid checklists: the Salento Peninsula as a case study	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13897618	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13897618

CoNISMa	Biological Data	Distributional/ Georeferenced data, poster	Biodiversity patterns in marine annelids associated to intertidal coralline algae along the Salento Peninsula	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14185213	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14185213
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Distributional/ Georeferenced data, poster	Marine annelids as models for innovative robots	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8042371	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/8042371

B. GENOMIC DATA

Biological material sampled during the project was preserved for genetic analyses and is deposited in the Museo di Biologia Marina of Porto Cesareo after processing. DNA extraction was carried out with a cost- and time-effective salting-out protocol on a small fragment of tissue, taking care of not damaging any diagnostic character of the preserved annelid. DNA was extracted from 422 individuals belonging to 202 morphospecies. Genetic characterization was obtained through two mitochondrial markers (the genes coding for the subunit I of the cytochrome c oxidase and the 16S Rrna); these markers were chosen as they are widely used in fauna species delimitation, and a good amount of baseline data on marine annelids is already available in public repositories. Useful sequences of at least one of the two markers were obtained for 143 morphospecies, while for the remaining 78 species sequences were not readable even in case of apparently successful amplification.

Regarding genomic data, the most common repositories are those presented in ANNEX IV. For the purposes of our project the Barcode of Life Data System (BOLD) was considered suitable and was used for genomic data submission. BOLD is an online workbench and database that supports the assembly and use of DNA barcode data. Regarding the relevant deliverable D2.3 “Integrated molecular/morphological identification of the species”, it has been uploaded in Zenodo as open access.

Table 3 Genomic data outputs and their repositories

Partner Contribution	Data Category	Data type	Title	DOI	Repository submitted	Relevant link
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Genomic data, Dataset	DNA sequencing	https://dx.doi.org/10.5883/DS-NATPOL25	BOLD Systems	https://portal.boldsystems.org/result?query=MWRM

CoNISMa	Biological Data	Genomic data, Deliverable	D2.3 Integrated molecular/morphological identification of the species	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13897531	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13897531
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Genomic data, Publication	First record of the non-indigenous Myrianida pachycera (Augener, 1913) (Annelida: Syllidae) in the Mediterranean Sea revealed by integrative taxonomy	https://doi.org/10.3391/bir.2025.14.3.16	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18661501
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Genomic data, Publication	Bridging past and present: the Salento Peninsula as a case study for unveiling marine annelid diversity by integrating literature, field surveys, and DNA barcoding	https://doi.org/10.1080/24750263.2026.2614131	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18661322
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Genomic data, Publication	Non-indigenous polychaetes along the Salento Peninsula: new records and first molecular data	https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.35851	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13843469

C. MORPHOLOGICAL AND BEHAVIORAL DATA

Data on annelid morphology, such as measurements, pictures, drawings belong to morphological data. Annelid measurements have been submitted to the MAPWORMS Zenodo community.

The morphological data, derived from the 2D/3D analysis of the micro-CT data, refer to the morphological description of the *Phascolosoma (Phascolosoma) stephensoni* (Sipuncula) and *Glycera tridactyla* (Polychaeta) specimens which have been selected as model species for the creation of the bio-inspired robot. In these scans, 2D and 3D analysis (e.g., volume, length of muscles, structure thickness etc.) have been performed, allowing for the characterization of several parameters for modelling the robot. In particular, the dataset comprising of the morphological data for these two annelid species was standardized and submitted in MedOBIS, following the same procedure as distributional/ georeferenced data.

As far as it concerns behavioral data, these refer to annelid behavior (footages, video formats, ethograms etc.).

The first measurements for the two main categories of potential model organisms which have been identified, and in particular the unsegmented Annelida (Sipuncula, Echiura) and Annelida with eversible, armed pharynx (Phyllodocida, Eunicida) are presented in Deliverable D2.2 “First set of parameters for modelling”. Standardised measurements of the external anatomy were performed on live individuals of *Phascolosoma stephensoni* in narrow aquaria filled with seawater using videos. In particular, frames from videos were analysed with the software ImageJ to obtain accurate measurements of the length and radius of the animals. After the characterization of the length and radius of the worms, additional tests were carried out to evaluate the speed of worms when moving in the aquaria filled with 0.5% agarose gel. The digging behavior of the worm in the filled aquaria was filmed.

Figure 3. Experimental video set-up used for the characterization of worms.

All the aforementioned measurements are provided in the Deliverables 2.2. and 2.4 which are uploaded in Zenodo and are openly available to any interested user outside the consortium. Furthermore, the analysis of the abovementioned data is presented in a recent publication [16].

Table 4 Morphological and behavioural data outputs and their repositories

Partner Contribution	Data Category	Data type	Title	DOI	Repository submitted	Relevant link
HCMR	Biological Data	Morphological and behavioral data, Dataset	Micro-CT Morphological Data of <i>Glycera tridactyla</i> Schmarda, 1861 and <i>Phascolosoma (Phascolosoma) stephensoni</i> (Stephen, 1942) species	https://doi.org/10.25607/mqd09f	a. MedOBIS b. OBIS c. GBIF	a. https://ipt.medobis.eu/resource?r=micro-ct_morphological_data_glycera_tridactyla_phascolosoma_stephensoni b. https://obis.org/dataset/74cc1af5-06e8-4c7e-9e87-0a862b9af5a9

						c. https://www.gbif.org/dataset/22fa3c39-2ff0-4f78-826f-bf526df17354
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Morphological and behavioral data, Deliverable	D2.2 First set of parameters for modelling	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13897604	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13897604
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Morphological and behavioral data, Deliverable	D2.4 Annelida performance final characterization	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18661112	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18661112

D. MICRO CT DATA

51 specimens belonging to Polychaeta and Sipuncula were scanned using the Skyscan 1172 micro-CT at HCMR to visualize their morphological and anatomical characteristics. From these specimens, 81 micro-CT scans (image data) have been generated, as many specimens were scanned both with and without contrast agents to visualize different structures (e.g., dense structures need to be scanned without contrast agents). A total of 76 datasets are publicly available, through the MicroCTvlab as shown in the Table below. It is noted that only a small number of scans were excluded due to insufficient image quality or limited informational value. Specifically, these datasets, along with their metadata, have been stored and uploaded to the Micro-CT virtual laboratory (<https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/>). This virtual lab offers a collection of virtual 3D specimens which are annotated with metadata and can be interactively displayed and retrieved through a web-based application [3]. MicroCTvlab has also an API (Application Programming Interface) in order to allow the user to get information on various micro-CT data scans, species information, and metadata related to the micro-CT dataset scans. A new collection for the MAPWORMS micro-CT scans has been created in the MicroCTvlab which is called MAPWORMS, in which all relative micro-CT scans have been uploaded (Figure 4).

In the MAPWORMS collection, by selecting a micro-CT dataset, the user has the ability to: a) see a short description of the scan with relative images, b) interact with the 3D representation of the sample using the web based Slice:Drop (<https://slicedrop.com/>) software, c) see a video of the scan and d) display the metadata for the dataset (Figure 5). Raw data can be downloaded through the metadata tab in .nifti format (.nii.gz). Images (in .png, .gif, .jpg or .jpeg format) and videos (in .mp4 format) can be also downloaded from the metadata tab.

To upload a micro-CT dataset please register first. ✕

Search Filters

Scientific Name

Sample Type

- Zoology
- Annelida
- Polychaeta
- Eunicida
- Lumbrineridae
- Lumbrineris
- Lumbrineris latreilli
- Eunicidae
- Eunice

Contrast Enhancement Method

- HMDS
- Iodine
- None
- PTA

Project

- BIOIMAGING-GR
- None
- ECCO
- MAPWORMS

Apply

Reset

Page 1 >>

Figure 4. The MAPWORMS specimen collection of the micro-CT scans

Figure 5. Features on the MicroCTlab.

Table 5 Micro-CT data outputs and their repositories.

Partner Contribution	Data Category	Data type	Title	DOI	Repository submitted	Relevant link
HCMR	Biological Data	Micro CT data, image data	MAPWORMS collection		a. MicroCTlab b. mobile web application	a. https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/ b. https://microct.app.hcmr.gr/
HCMR	Biological Data	Micro CT data, protocols	MAPWORMS Micro-CT imaging protocols	https://doi.org/10.1/zenodo.1403980	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/1403980

2.2 TECHNICAL DATA

Apart from Biological Data presented in the previous section, and referred to WP2 activities, technical data are also part of the MAPWORMS project. Technical data consist of five different types of data (Table 1), which are presented below. Technical data (including raw data, deliverables and publications) are stored to MAPWORMS Zenodo community.

- a. Modelling data
- b. Laser characterization data
- c. Anatomical modelling data
- d. Experimental data
- e. Morphing data

A. **MODELLING DATA**

Modelling data, such as codes, software, mechanical simulations, and images were produced within WP3. WP3 aimed to develop theoretical and numerical tools to model the shape changes of thin sheets driven by the modulation of internal stresses and stiffness variations (algorithmic morphing). The shape changing capabilities of these thin sheets were inspired by the shape changing capabilities of marine Annelida, and formed the basis of the design of worm-inspired robots based on stimuli-responsive materials with controllable stiffness.

Modelling data came from: dedicated characterization/design process, i.e., mechanical/visual characterization through i) Instron material testing machine, ii) load cells, iii) Hyrox; software for realization process through specific machines (soft materials 3D printer, laser cutter); simulation software; CAD design. Data are strictly connected to the used hardware and in the specific project dedicated systems (gel or characterization set ups) are created. The tools used in order to access these types of data come mainly with a fee (MATLAB, LabVIEW, CAD software such as SolidWork, COMSOL), but there is some open-source software such as Arduino and Repetier-Host. Modelling data are available through open access publications, as well as through Zenodo.

To reproduce some of the behaviors of Sipuncula and similar marine worms, it is considered helpful to model them in a way that is simple enough to be translated into the design and optimization of an artificial device, that is, models that can cover the gap between biology and technology. To do this, the **SSSA** team building on what has been presented in Deliverables D2.2, D2.3, D2.4 and D3.1, has developed several 3D models based on the notion of multiplicative decomposition of the deformation gradient, that can be adopted to mimic worm behaviors by means of actively imposing a target 3D metric tensor. This mechanism is particularly useful as it can be easily adapted to different actuation strategies and it is presented in D3.2 and D3.3, which are openly available at Zenodo MAPWORMS community.

The following table presents all available modelling data (raw data, deliverables and publications) and their repository through which can be accessible.

Table 6 Modelling data outputs and their repositories

Partner Contribution	Data Category	Data type	Title	DOI	Repository submitted	Relevant link
SSSA	Technical Data	Modelling data, Deliverable	D3.1 Validated morphing algorithm for smart hydrogels based on non-euclidean plates	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14199334	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14199334
SSSA	Technical Data	Modelling data, Deliverable	D3.2 Validated direct morphing FEM algorithms	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14199377	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14199377
SSSA	Technical Data	Modelling data, Deliverable	D3.3 Morphing of structures: inverse IBV problem	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18846589	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18846589
SSSA	Technical Data	Modelling data, poster	Modeling McKibben artificial muscles through differential geometry	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8028524	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/8028524
SSSA	Technical Data	Modelling data, Dataset	Mechanical characterization of agar gel	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19091582	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/19091582
SSSA	Technical Data	Modelling data, Dataset	2D COMSOL simulation of magnetic bender	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19090617	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/19090617

B. LASER CHARACTERIZATION DATA

Technical data in the form of datasheets were generated by **VEXLUM**, during the process of characterization of the laser systems. VEXLUM has an increasing exposure to quantum technology, semiconductor metrology, and laser medicine applications, where OEM lasers with specific wavelengths requirements (some of them overlapping with MAPWORMS targets) are in high demand, particularly when it comes to the ability to tailor the wavelengths and ensure a compact form factor and cost-effectiveness. An example of a

laser characterization report (datasheet) is openly available in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/13939007>). It is noted that laser characterization data are considered sensitive, as the commercial outcome is very promising. There is strong demand for high-power, compact semiconductor lasers in the 8xx nm and 4xx nm wavelength ranges.

Table 7 Laser characterisation data outputs and their repositories

Partner Contribution	Data Category	Data type	Title	DOI	Repository submitted	Relevant link
VEXLUM	Technical Data	Laser characterization data, Deliverable	D5.3 Laser system for light stimulation	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18846117	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18846117
VEXLUM	Technical Data	Laser characterization data, Datasheet	VEXLUM, laser characterization report	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13939007	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13939007
VEXLUM	Technical Data	Laser characterization data, presentation	Progress of turnkey VECSEL systems for quantum technology	https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2656414	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/8046794

C. ANATOMICAL MODELLING DATA

In addition to the modelling data used for computer simulation generated in WP3, **ACMIT** has also used and generated modelling data for the development of appropriate testing environments in WP6, which are anatomical models (also called phantoms) for proposed medical use-cases. These anatomical modelling data includes data of the human anatomy, which is taken from segmented medical images. In the current project, only available data were used – for the brain phantom, data from a previous project at ACMIT was used, the medical imaging data building the basis for the nose model was taken from an open online repository on Zenodo ([NasalSeq](#)) and the idealized stomach and colon geometries were acquired from an online 3D model store ([cgtrader](#)). In addition, data on material properties (of human tissue and artificial materials) were needed, similar to mechanical property data in the computer simulation. This data has been taken from literature for the brain ^{[10], [11]}, colon^[17], and stomach ^{[12] [13]} as well as previously performed material tests ^[14]. Based on the anatomy and material data, models were designed using 3D Slicer and CAD-Software (e.g., Solidworks, Fusion 360) and g-Code files for 3D-printing were generated using PrusaSlicer. As most of the data generated is either sensitive (ACMIT

also has a webshop for anatomical models) or only in an experimental state, the only data that can be shared in this category is the data sheet of the developed brain phantom.

Table 8 Anatomical data outputs and their repositories

Partner Contribution	Data Category	Data type	Title	DOI	Repository submitted	Relevant link
ACMIT	Technical Data	Data Sheet	Brain phantom data sheet	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19733305	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/19733305

D. EXPERIMENTAL DATA

WP4 deals with experimental data, including the synthesis, characterization and applications of stimuli-responsive hydrogels and cryogels, surface-immobilised gels, and hydrogel microcapsules. The HUJI laboratory's prior expertise and achievements were used to guide the design of these novel hydrogels. Established methodologies served as a foundation for developing the new hydrogel materials. These data are well described through scientific publications [4], [5], [6] which are stored in Zenodo, along with the relevant deliverables as indicated in the table below.

Within WP4, **HUJI**'s research activities addressed two primary objectives:

- (i) the development of new concepts and approaches for designing bulk stimuli-responsive hydrogels, while identifying possible applications of these gels for controlled-release, shape-morphing, and self-healing, and
- (ii) the development of methodologies for integrating different stimuli-responsive gels with surfaces, along with identifying potential applications for these gel-modified surfaces.

Specifically, Deliverables 4.1 and 4.3 introduced the concept of switchable and/or transient stimuli-responsive gel matrices exhibiting controlled stiffness properties, and dissipative transient stiffness properties as bulk soft materials. These stimuli-responsive transient gels were implemented for transient, controlled load-release, self-healing, and soft-robotic actuation. Different triggers, including biological (glucose) or chemical agents, pH, redox, and light, were used to activate the dynamic properties of the different gel matrices.

In parallel, Deliverables 4.2 and 4.4 developed methods to integrate switchable gels and the transient gels (a new class of gels) on surface supports. These included the deposition of the gels on loaded microparticle templates and the application of the hybrid system to yield (after an acid-based etching process) redox-responsive transient dissipative hydrogel microcapsule frameworks. Alternatively, the stimuli-responsive gels were deposited on conductive Au-coated surfaces and loaded with different desired loads.

Chemical/photochemical/light multimodal-triggered release of the loads from surface-confined matrices was demonstrated.

Overall, the results generated within WP4 demonstrate significant application potential. In particular, the developed systems provide promising opportunities for controlled transient load release in biomedical applications, and agriculture, as well as for the development of autonomously driven soft-robotic systems.

Table 9 Experimental data outputs and their repositories

Partner Contribution	Data Category	Data type	Title	DOI	Repository submitted	Relevant link
HUJI	Technical Data	Experimental Data, Deliverable	D4.1 - Delivery of available smart responsive hydrogels for preliminary modelling and for devising integration possibilities	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8041622	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/8041622
HUJI	Technical Data	Experimental Data, Deliverable	D4.2 - Immobilized stimuli-responsive hydrogels on surfaces	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14199396	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14199396
HUJI	Technical Data	Experimental Data, Deliverable	D4.3 Synthesis and characterisation of shape-memory and self-healing hydrogels	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18648239	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18648239
HUJI	Technical Data	Experimental Data, Deliverable	D4.4 Immobilized stimuli-responsive hydrogels on surfaces - update	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18648369	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18648369
HUJI	Technical Data	Experimental Data, publication	Chemical and Photochemical-Driven Dissipative Fe ³⁺ /Fe ²⁺ -Ion Cross-Linked Carboxymethyl Cellulose Gels Operating Under Aerobic Conditions: Applications for Transient Controlled Release and	https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.4c00625?urlapp=nd=%3Fref%3DPDF&jav=VoR&rel=cite-as	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/10980500

			Mechanical Actuation			
HUJI	Technical Data	Experimental Data, publication	Stiffness-Switchable, Biocatalytic pH-Responsive DNA-Functionalized Polyacrylamide Cryogels and their Mechanical Applications	https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202306586	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/10980332
HUJI	Technical Data	Experimental Data, publication and supporting material (raw data)	Stimuli-Responsive DNA-Based Hydrogels on Surfaces for Switchable Bioelectrocatalysis and Controlled Release of Loads	https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.3c06230	Zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19119159

E. MORPHING DATA

In WP5, **SSSA** worked on the development of new soft robotics solutions integrating responsiveness to external stimuli to better mimic biological organism reactions to the environment, thus enabling morphing adaptation. The robots' ability to adapt and react to the environment was also tested with a view to applications in different research fields, e.g., medical domains. These data are considered as Morphing data of this project and relevant deliverables along with raw data are stored in Zenodo (see Table 10 below).

Specifically, the MAPWORMS project introduced innovative soft robotic concepts inspired by the shape morphing abilities of marine worms, particularly Sipuncula. The project aimed to develop worm-inspired soft robots created through the assembly of various actuation units capable of simple primitive movements and responsive to stimuli such as magnetic fields and pressure within smart architectures.

Magnetic-responsive bending and twisting actuation units have been developed and combined in the form of robots to achieve peristaltic-type motions and eversion mechanisms. An eversible robot capable of extending a proboscis-like structure, and a peristaltic robot capable of locomotion and load carrying capabilities were demonstrated. These results have been reported in two scientific articles currently under review.

Pressure-responsive actuation units were developed and combined to achieve peristaltic-type motions and eversion mechanism through triangular and hexagonal vesicle structures. The performance of these vesicles was assessed in terms of strain, force generation, and volume variation. These results are currently being reported in scientific articles under preparation.

Table 10 Morphing data outputs and their repositories

Partner Contribution	Data Category	Data type	Title	DOI	Repository submitted	Relevant link
SSSA	Technical Data	Morphing Data, Deliverable	D5.1 - First working actuation unit	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14199421	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14199421
SSSA	Technical Data	Morphing Data, Deliverable	D5.2 - First version of actuation units combination	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14199474	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14199474
SSSA	Technical Data	Morphing data raw	Magnetically-Driven Deployable Structure Inspired by Worms	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18221609	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18221609
SSSA	Technical Data	Morphing data, Poster	Worm-Inspired Soft Robot with Magnetically Driven Eversible Proboscis	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18219665	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18219665
SSSA	Technical Data	Morphing data, Poster	Mimicking Adaptation and Plasticity in WORMS: the MAPWORMS Project	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7912991	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/7912991
SSSA	Technical Data	Morphing data, Publication	A Bioinspired Fluid-Filled Soft Linear Actuator	https://doi.org/10.1089/soro.2021.0091	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/7866839
SSSA	Technical Data	Morphing data, Publication and raw data	Unsegmented marine annelids as biomechanical models for soft robotics	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-026-44047-w	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/19088049

SSSA	Technical Data	Morphing data, poster	Reconfigurable Soft Magnetic Architectures for Deployable Morphing Structures	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19387862	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/19387862
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2.3 PATENT-SEARCH DATA

According to WP6, patent-search data were acquired related to all concepts of soft robotic actuators studied within the MAPWORMS project and their potential medical applications. These concepts could be assigned to three main research areas, which are hydrogels, magnetic actuation, and fluid-based eversion.

As it is stated in D.6.3 – Final IP report, a broad patent search was performed within these areas, complemented by more detailed searches for the specifically defined Key Exploitable Results of the project, which can be assigned to these three basic areas as well as to the named innovations in the Innovation Radar report. Patent searches were carried out using Espacenet, and the potentially interesting patents were stored in a database in the commercial patent managing program PatOffice. Within this database, patents were assigned to one of the defined KERs and their relevance for the project was rated by two ACMIT members on a scale from 0 to 3 stars. Reports were generated for each of the 3 research areas including the patents with 2- and 3-stars rankings. These reports were sent out to the partner responsible for the respective research areas and further evaluation of these patents was performed together with the partner, resulting in a final rating. The most relevant patents and their final ratings were then also reported in D.6.3, together with some interpretation and conclusions with regard to the IP handling within the project. A short summary of the IP handling as well as further exploitation of project results is also included in deliverable D1.16 – Updated dissemination, communication and exploitation plan.

Table 11 Patent search data outputs and their repositories

Partner Contribution	Data Category	Data type	Title	DOI	Repository submitted	Relevant link
ACMIT	Patent-search Data	Deliverable	D6.1 - Preliminary IP report	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8041663	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/8041663
ACMIT	Patent-search Data	Deliverable	D6.2 - Report on task primitives' definition and self-healing hydrogels	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14199540	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14199540

ACMIT	Patent-search Data	Deliverable	D6.3 - Final IP Report	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18936934	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18936934
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2.4 DISSEMINATION DATA

Dissemination data refers to any information released during the MAPWORMS project through social media, its official website and the scientific publications. According to the D1.2 (MAPWORMS_D1.2_project handbook_v5_20220729), when results (e.g., presentation, article, etc.) obtained within a WP were intended to be published by a partner, the WP leader and the IM had to be informed. Furthermore, the Article 17 in the MAPWORMS Grant Agreement mentions that *“a beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give at least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate. Any other beneficiary may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.”* A comprehensive list of the dissemination data can be found in D1.16 – Updated dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and in D1.5, D1.8 and D1.12 – Annual reports on key communication events.

Dissemination data can be also related to those used in exhibitions or in web platforms and mobile applications. For example, micro-CT data have been disseminated through a touchscreen monitor using the DrishtiPrayog open source software at the [InnoDays](#) innovation exhibition during 24-26 November 2023, organized by the Region of Crete (Figure 7). These data may also be disseminated using the same software at the Cretaquarium at the end of the project.

Figure 7. Micro-CT datasets disseminated at the Innodays exhibition.

Micro-CT data were also disseminated through a mobile web application (<https://microctapp.hcmr.gr/>) developed on Wordpress CMS with the use of the Web Apps (PWA) plugin (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Mobile application for the dissemination of micro-CT data

From March 23rd to 27th, 2026, the MAPWORMS project was actively involved in the European Robotics Forum (ERF) held in Stavanger, Norway— one of the most important annual gatherings for the European robotics community. More information related to this event along with all dissemination efforts of the MAPWORM team can be found on the official website (<https://www.mapworms.eu/news-events/>). The table below presents the dissemination data that are hosted in Zenodo.

Table 12 Dissemination data outputs and their repositories

Partner Contribution	Data Category	Data type	Title	DOI	Repository submitted	Relevant link
All	Dissemination Data	video	MAPWORMS - Mimicking Adaptation and Plasticity in WORMS	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14246963	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14246963
All	Dissemination Data	video	PROJECT'S OVERVIEW VIDEO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13939616	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13939616
SSSA	Dissemination Data	deliverable	D1.1 - Website and Project LOGO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13906912	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13906912

						https://zenodo.org/records/13906912
SSSA	Dissemination Data	deliverable	D1.4 - Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8039651	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/8039651
SSSA	Dissemination Data	deliverable	D1.5 - Annual report on key communication events	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13906885	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13906885
SSSA	Dissemination Data	deliverable	D1.8 - Report on Key Communication Events - 2nd Reporting Period	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14199272	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14199272
HCMR	Dissemination Data	poster	Scientific community needs: FAIR and credible data repositories. The case of MedOBIS Repository and MAPWORMS Project	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13827761	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13827761
HCMR	Dissemination Data	presentation	Applying FAIR principles to Micro-CT data, the case of MAPWORMS PROJECT	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13683253	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13683253
SSSA	Dissemination Data	video	Video presenting 3D printing	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13939664	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13939664
HCMR SSSA CoNISMα	Dissemination Data	poster	poster (in Greek) presented at the "Crete and Sea" event, organized by HCMR and FORTH, Crete, Greece	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19230960	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/19230960

3 FAIR DATA

MAPWORMS supported the concept of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data and has therefore invested in making its research outputs compliant with FAIR principles. This did not necessarily mean that all project data remained fully open. Instead, the project followed the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary". This approach encourages sharing data to accelerate research, while restricting access only when required for intellectual property and commercial interest.

MAPWORMS research outputs were stored in Zenodo community. Communities of Zenodo are considered as shared areas that allows research projects to gather, organize, and showcase their research outputs (datasets, software, publications). Figure 9 shows

analytically where the MAPWORMS research outputs were stored. It is highlighted that MAPWORMS Zenodo community was used as the main generic repository for the project; while for Biological data (distributional, morphological, genetic data) specific-domain repositories were used in addition to enhance findability and reusability of data. It is also worth mentioning that special effort has been spent to standardise the biological data according to the standards that are applied to those domain-specific repositories such as OBIS and GBIF.

Figure 9. Graph showing the MAPWORMS research outputs and the repositories in which are stored.

As illustrated in the graph above, the selected domain-specific repositories include MedOBIS, OBIS, and GBIF for biogeographic marine data, BOLD Systems for DNA data and MicroCTvLab for scans. Particular emphasis is placed on MedOBIS, which is hosted by the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, and whose Node Manager also serves as the Data Manager responsible for this Data Management Plan (DMP). MedOBIS is interconnected with major global data aggregators, as shown in Figure 10, including OBIS, GBIF, EMODnet, and LifeWatch ERIC. All the above-mentioned repositories operate using the Darwin Core standards.

Figure 10: International data flow schema. Source: EurOBIS (www.eurobis.org), accessed on 2026-04-01 [15]

Table 13, presents the comprehensive list of the project deliverables along with their dissemination level and their publication status in the MAPWORMS Zenodo community. Regarding the protocols followed during the project, all of them are presented in detail in the selected repositories and in publications in order to increase visibility and reproducibility for any interested users.

Within this framework, patent-search data remain restricted and all relevant deliverables (D6.1, D6.2 and D6.3) with a “sensitive” dissemination level were stored with restricted access in MAPWORMS community in Zenodo. Nevertheless, their metadata are publicly available and include contact information so that interested users can reach out to request further details. Apart from the patent-search data, the data regarding the validated morphing algorithm for smart hydrogels and the laser system for light stimulation were also considered sensitive.

On the other hand, annelid behavior data (footages, ethograms, video formats, etc.) and immobilized stimuli responsive hydrogels on surfaces, which were initially considered sensitive for patenting purposes, were ultimately made public and accessible to any interested user outside the consortium.

Finally, it is worth mentioning, that special effort was focused on increasing the FAIRness status of Micro CT data. This effort is described in the publication entitled “Applying FAIR principles to Micro-CT data, the case of MAPWORMS project”, presented at the

5th International Congress on Applied Ichthyology, Oceanography, and Aquatic Environment (HydroMediT 2024) [7].

TABLE 13 COMPREHENSIVE LIST OF DELIVERABLES AND THEIR DISSEMINATION STATUS

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Zenodo MAPWORMS Community
D1.1	Website and Project LOGO	WP1	PU – Public	√
D1.2	Project management handbook	WP1	PU – Public	√
D1.3	FAIR-compliant Data Management Plan	WP1	PU – Public	√
D1.4	Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan	WP1	PU – Public	√
D1.5	Annual report on key communication events	WP1	PU – Public	√
D1.6	Technical/Scientific review meeting documents	WP1	SEN-Sensitive	√
D1.7	RP2 update of the Data Management Plan	WP1	PU – Public	√
D1.8	Report on key communication events – 2 nd reporting period	WP1	PU – Public	√
D1.9	Technical/Scientific 2 nd review meeting documents	WP1	SEN-Sensitive	Available when finalized
D1.10	Report on Virtual galleries of the Voucher Specimens Collection	WP1	PU – Public	Available when finalized
D1.11	RP3 update of the Data Management Plan	WP1	PU – Public	Available when finalized
D1.12	Reports on key communication event – 3 rd reporting period	WP1	PU – Public	Available when finalized
D1.13	Final report on MAPWORMS workshops	WP1	PU – Public	Available when finalized
D1.14	Technical/Scientific 3 rd review meeting documents	WP1	SEN-Sensitive	Available when finalized
D1.15	Final project report	WP1	PU – Public	Available when finalized
D1.16	Updated dissemination, communication and exploitation plan	WP1	PU – Public	Available when finalized
D2.1	Georeferenced Annelida distribution map along the Apulia coast	WP2	PU – Public	√
D2.2	First set of parameters for modelling	WP2	PU – Public	√
D2.3	Integrated molecular/morphological identification of the species	WP2	SEN-Sensitive PU – Public	√*
D2.4	Annelida performance final characterization	WP2	SEN-Sensitive PU – Public	√*
D3.1	Validated morphing algorithm for smart hydrogels based on non-Euclidean plates	WP3	SEN-Sensitive	√
D3.2	Validated direct morphing FEM algorithm	WP3	PU – Public	√
D3.3	Validated inverse morphing FEM algorithm	WP3	PU – Public	√
D4.1	Delivery of available smart responsive hydrogels for preliminary modelling and for devising integration possibilities	WP4	PU – Public	√
D4.2	Immobilized stimuli-responsive hydrogels on surfaces	WP4	SEN-Sensitive PU – Public	√*

D4.3	Synthesis, characterization of shape-memory/self-healing hydrogels	WP4	SEN-Sensitive PU – Public	√*
D4.4	Immobilized stimuli-responsive hydrogels on surfaces – UPDATE	WP4	SEN-Sensitive PU – Public	√*
D5.1	First working actuation unit	WP5	PU – Public	√
D5.2	First version of actuation units' combination	WP5	PU – Public	√
D5.3	Laser system for light stimulation	WP5	SEN-Sensitive	√
D5.4	Morphing robot first report	WP5	PU – Public	Available when finalized
D5.5	Morphing robot final report	WP5	PU – Public	Available when finalized
D6.1	Preliminary IP report	WP6	SEN-Sensitive	√
D6.2	Report on task primitives' definition	WP6	SEN-Sensitive	√
D6.3	Final IP report	WP6	SEN-Sensitive	√
D6.4	Validation of the shape morphing robot in selected application scenarios	WP6	PU – Public	Available when finalized

* This asterisk indicates that although the deliverable status was initially sensitive, following internal consultation between the Lead Beneficiary and the Data Manager, the dissemination level was set to public.

3.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

In order to ensure the findability of all data produced by the MAPWORMS project, the following four principles (F1-F4) were supported in this DMP according to the FAIR guide ^[8] and the Horizon 2020 Online Manual ^[9]:

F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier: Each dataset, deliverable, and research output received a persistent identifier (PID) such as a DOI. Persistent identifiers allow data to be reliably cited, indexed, and discovered over time. This is exactly the reason why all repositories proposed and used through the project (ANNEX VII) are using globally unique and persistent identifiers to remove ambiguity. Even the restricted outputs, were assigned with a DOI as shown in tables 2 - 12.

Only exception is the MicroCTvLab which does not assign DOIs. However, this repository is hosted at the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research which keeps it active over time – through its Network Operations Center (NOC). Furthermore, each dataset uploaded in the MicroCTvLab has been assigned with a unique identifier resulting in a unique URL for each dataset.

F2. Data are described with rich metadata: MAPWORMS project outputs were described with rich metadata (descriptive information about the data). All partners were encouraged to be generous and extensive when providing metadata information. The concept is that even if the data are not available, at least they are described by rich metadata.

The repositories used (ANNEX VII), have mandatory metadata fields that need to be filled. For example, Zenodo, which is being used as a repository for all types of research outputs (e.g., datasets, deliverables, publications, videos) has a standard metadata catalogue which guided the partners for the appropriate metadata fields. Regarding the micro-CT datasets, there are no metadata standards, however the MicroCTvLab offers an extensive list of rich metadata (ANNEX VI) with mandatory metadata fields.

According to the Article 17 of the MAPWORMS grant agreement, metadata of the deposited publications were licensed under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC0), and provide information at least about the following:

- a. publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue)
- b. Horizon Europe funding
- c. grant project, name, acronym and number
- d. licensing terms
- e. persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organizations and the grant.
- f. persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication (where applicable)

In the case of metadata of deposited data, these remained open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC0) (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded) in accordance with Article 17. Furthermore, these metadata provide information at least about the following:

- a) datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo)
- b) Horizon Europe funding
- c) grant project name, acronym and number
- d) licensing terms
- e) persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organizations and the grant
- f) persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs (where applicable)

F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe: metadata and the dataset they describe are usually separate files, thus the association between a metadata file and the dataset have been made explicit by mentioning the dataset globally unique and persistent identifier in the metadata field of the selected repositories (e.g., Zenodo, MedOBIS, OBIS, GBIF).

F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource: datasets were uploaded and published in well-known repositories (see ANNEX IV and ANNEX VII).

Naming conventions are very important as consistent naming increases the findability of the project data. The D1.2 (MAPWORMS_D1.2_project handbook_v5_20220729) has set up the rules for the naming convention of the work package and deliverable reports (Table). Each partner was responsible to upload the updated versions of their data with the appropriate naming convention and the appropriate version number. Relative keywords have been provided based on the naming conventions and the metadata. MAPWORMS datasets available in Zenodo MAPWORMS community were standardised according to MAPWORMS naming conventions and were enriched with metadata records in accordance with the Article 17 of the MAPWORMS grant agreement.

Table 14 MAPWORMS naming conventions

TYPE OF DOCUMENT	NAME OF THE FILE
Work package report or other project	MAPWORMS_WP[xx]_[kindofreport]_[shorttitle]_rev[xx]_yyyymmdd
Deliverable report	MAPWORMS_D[xx]_[shorttitle]_rev[xx]_yyyymmdd
Data files	MAPWORMS_PartnerName_[shorttitle]_version number[xx]_yyyymmdd

3.2 MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

MAPWORMS data can be accessed and explored using various software tools. Most of these data are provided in formats that can be accessed and used through open-source software. In particular, MedOBIS for georeferenced data uses the Integrated Publishing Tool, which is a free open-source software developed by GBIF and used by organizations around the world to create and manage repositories for sharing biodiversity datasets. Regarding micro-CT data, MicroCTvLab uses the Slice-Drop, which is an open-source, interactive visualization tool that allows users to visualize imaging data in three dimensions. In addition, Zenodo is an open repository that allows for sharing and preserving data of any size and format. Zenodo code is also open source, built on the open source Invenio digital library. Furthermore, metadata in Zenodo are available under CC0 license, and all open content is accessible through open APIs.

During the project life, according to Table 1, non-open-source software was also used (e.g., Dragonfly software, for which there is a free license for researchers with non-commercial activities). Though, the outcomes of the analysis that is deposited in Zenodo is openly accessible.

To ensure the accessibility of all produced data by the MAPWORMS project, the following two principles (A1-A2) were supported in this DMP according to the FAIR guide ^[8] and the Horizon 2020 Online Manual ^[9]:

A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communication protocol: A well-organized documentation system and a fully mechanized protocol ensures freely accessible data through the selected repositories. Regarding sensitive data, these are guaranteed as FAIR by providing contact details of the responsible contact person. These details are explicitly included in the metadata field of the selected Repositories.

A2. Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available: This DMP targeted to relate to well-known and well-maintained repositories. In cases of data unavailability, it is crucial to be able to trace people, institutions or publications associated with the original research. Therefore, this DMP emphasized the necessity of Metadata availability.

In particular in Zenodo, all metadata were stored in JSON-format and can be exported in several standard formats (e.g., MARCXML, Dublin Core, and DataCite Metadata Schema; according to the OpenAIRE Guidelines.

According to the D1.2 (MAPWORMS_D1.2_project handbook_v5_20220729), five types of documents were produced according to their dissemination and confidentiality level:

- PU – Public, fully open, e.g., web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)
- SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Currently, the MAPWORMS Zenodo Community hosts, apart from public data, also data with restricted access. Throughout the project the target was to maintain balance between the IP and Open access strategies of the data through constant communication with the IM, the IMB and the DM.

Regarding scientific publications, in general, MAPWORMS project supported, where possible, an Open Access Strategy based on the Guidelines about the rules on Open Access to Scientific publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020 (Figure).

MAPWORMS project mainly aimed to publish its project results as “gold” open access in order to increase the accessibility of the obtained results. When the “gold” open access

publishing was not applicable (e.g., conference proceedings or abstract), the “green” open access was adopted where authors can make pre-prints available to the wider community.

Currently, the MAPWORMS Zenodo Community hosts 9 posters, 2 presentations, 1 data paper and 9 publications.

Figure 11 Open access strategy for the access and reuse of research data. Modified image from [9]

3.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

In order to make the MAPWORMS data interoperable the following three principles (I1-I3) are supported in this DMP according to the FAIR guide [8] and the Horizon 2020 Online Manual [9]:

I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation. In other words, it should be possible for people and computers to interpret both metadata and data of the project and be able to combine it with other datasets. This principle prerequisites to include proper documentation while making your data available, use preferred and common file formats and clear dataset structures. All the aforementioned features are achieved through the use of repositories such as Zenodo

and file formats (see Table 1) that are acceptable and commonly used through the research community.

12. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles. MAPWORMS datasets have been standardized according to controlled vocabularies, such as Darwin Core Standards for transmitting information about biodiversity and Marine Regions for localities. These vocabularies use globally unique and persistent identifiers (e.g., links).

13. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data. In this context, all datasets have been properly cited (i.e., including their globally unique and persistent identifiers), and used controlled vocabularies and ontologies, such as Darwin Core standards for distributional data. The Darwin Core standard includes a glossary of terms intended to facilitate the sharing of information about biological diversity by providing identifiers, labels, and definitions.

Other examples of controlled vocabularies and ontologies, are: a) the worms taxonomic mapping (<https://www.marinespecies.org/index.php>), which is an authoritative classification and catalogue of marine species names maintained at the Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ); and b) the Marine Regions application (<https://www.marineregions.org/>), which is a standard list of marine georeferenced place names and areas.

3.4 INCREASE DATA RE-USE (THROUGH CLARIFYING LICENCES)

In order to optimize the reuse of the produced data by the MAPWORMS project from any interested user, the following principle (R1) is supported in this DMP according to the FAIR guide ^[8] and the Horizon 2020 Online Manual ^[9]:

R1. (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes: each data owner has provided in close collaboration with Data Manager rich metadata which describe all the aspects of the data generation (e.g., experimental protocols followed, species used, search keywords etc.). In this framework, the metadata fields for Micro CT have been updated and included new obligatory information related to citation, data license, dataset url, publication date, scientificNameID (see ANNEX VI).

Furthermore, in order to increase the discoverability of the data, a clear licensing status is important for the users and the machines. For this reason, MAPWORMS DMP have supported since the beginning of the project the Creative Commons License. There are several types of Creative Commons licenses which differ regarding the terms of data distribution. For MAPWORMS metadata the selected license is Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC0). CC0 allows the users to freely build upon, enhance and reuse the MAPWORMS metadata without restriction under copyright or database law. For MAPWORMS data, the available option has been CC BY, which allows the reuse of data (and for commercial use) with the appropriate credit.

Most of the MAPWORMS data are openly available for re-use to interested users. In the project lifetime, at some point an embargo period has been set for several data types, mainly for publication reasons and for patent-search to be filed. This embargo period was over after the end of the project. On the other hand, sensitive data remained restricted even after the end of the project.

As a general comment, for our FAIR strategy, is that to stimulate discovery and potential re-use of the metadata and data, MAPWORMS maximally exploited existing data flow pathways to share data through well-known European e-infrastructures, such as EMODnet and LifeWatch and global initiatives like OBIS and GBIF.

4 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Data management is included in WP1. Ms. Dimitra Mavraki was appointed as a Data Manager (DM) for the Data Management Plan (DMP) handling during the MAPWORMS kickoff meeting, on the 13th of May 2022, in Pisa. Ms. Dimitra Mavraki is an Environmental Scientist with post-graduate studies on Hydrology and Environmental Management of Water Resources. She has been working as Data Manager at the HCMR, since 2013. She is specialized in marine data collection and digitization, quality control and standardization of both new and historical data, FAIR Principles to marine (meta)data, open access E-infrastructures and Repositories. She has 18 relevant publications and in 2019 she was a Grant winner as an expert European Researcher & Scientist working with data to attend the 14th Research Data Alliance Plenary meeting, in Helsinki, under the theme "Data Makes the Difference". The role of DM was to work closely with each partner in order to guide on how to make MAPWORMS data FAIR. Besides the management of produced data, mainly allocated by HCMR, all the partners have allocated a dedicated budget for handling and disseminating their data.

During the project, MAPWORMS data were linked to the key European integrating data infrastructures and repositories (MedOBIS, OBIS, GBIF, Zenodo, MicroCTvLab) which provide long-term preservation of the data. Further details about the selected repositories can be found in ANNEX IV and VII.

5 DATA SECURITY

MAPWORMS website (<https://www.mapworms.eu/>) is hosted on the Aruba provider (<https://www.aruba.it/>) and has adopted the following protection measures:

- *Anti-DdoS protection.* The DDoS attack is fought by analyzing incoming data, detecting abnormal traffic and, where possible, blocking potentially dangerous packages.
- *Firewalls and WAFs.* Servers' firewalls protect machines' access ports from unauthorized external connections.

- *IDS systems.* Thanks to Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS), the website is constantly monitored from potentially harmful calls in order to intervene with appropriate precautionary blocking measures.
- *Blocking malicious IPs.* Constant monitoring of the main blacklists permits to pre-emptively block any attempts to access your site from any of the reported IP addresses.

Regarding data security and website integrity, these backups were made:

- the provider automatically makes a daily and a weekly backup hosted in the space used for the website and accessible only by ftp;
- a manual backup is performed by the SSSA team every month and stored on a device disconnected from the network.

As reported in the D1.1 (MAPWORMS_D1.1_Website and Project LOGO_V4), MAPWORMS website is also exploitable as a gateway to a private repository platform for the Consortium and only available to registered partners. To protect the registered users' accounts and data from unauthorized access all users had systematically changed their login password (every 90 days).

Only the SSSA team could access the website storage area to upload reports, results data etc. This private area of the website did not allow for the modification of documents but only the possibility to upload (only by the SSSA team) and download (by the other registered users) of these documents.

Regarding, the **MicroCT website** (<https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/>) it is hosted on the HCMR provider (<https://www.hcmr.gr/>), which adopts the following protection measures:

- Anti - DoS protection. DDoS attacks are countered by examining incoming data, identifying unusual traffic, and blocking potentially harmful packets where feasible.
- Firewalls. Servers' firewalls protect internal networks from unauthorised external access.
- Intrusion Detection and Prevention Systems (IDPS). These monitor network traffic for suspicious activities and potential threats, automatically alerting administrators or blocking access.
- Preventing access from harmful IPs. Continuous surveillance of key blacklists allows for proactively blocking any attempts to reach your site from flagged IP addresses.

Regarding data security and website integrity, HCMR provider automatically created daily and weekly backups, stored in the space allocated for the website and accessible exclusively via FTP.

The MicroCTvlab website was developed using the Drupal CMS. To protect the website, the Drupal core and all modules were kept up to date. Additionally, security modules were used, including the Security Review Module for performing automated security checks,

Captcha and the reCaptcha to protect against bots and automated attacks, the HoneyPot Module which helps reduce form spam by adding hidden fields invisible to human users but capable of trapping bots and the Password Policy which enforces strong password requirements such as complexity, expiration, and reuse prevention.

The MAPWORMS project worked in collaboration with the major ocean Data Research Infrastructures, which have the mandate for long-term data curation and preservation. Zenodo is also a safe certified repository as data are stored in CERN'S Data Centre and it is built and operated by CERN and OpenAIRE. Furthermore, the DM has created a dedicated MAPWORMS community in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/>) which increased the data curation through the acceptance or rejection of data input in the community collection. MAPWORMS results are linked with the MAPWORMS Zenodo community. Details about the selected repositories can be found in ANNEX VII.

6 ETHICAL ASPECTS

All ethical aspects of this project are covered in the Ethics Self-Assessment section (pages 21-22) in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Based on the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR- <https://gdpr.eu/>), project partners were responsible for the handling of personal data involved in their activities. MAPWORMS project did not transfer personal data to any other entities.

National legislation was followed regarding sampling of species. National and European data protection regulations were followed.

7 REFERENCES

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ANNEX I ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Meaning
ACMIT	Austrian Center for Medical Innovation and Technology
CoNISMa	Consorzio Nazionale Interuniversitario per le Scienze del Mare
DM	Data Manager
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EMODNET	European Marine Observation and Data Network
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
HCMR	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research
HUJI	Hebrew University of Jerusalem
IM	Innovation Manager
IMB	Innovation Management Board
IP	Intellectual Property
IPT	Integrated Publishing Toolkit
MedOBIS	Mediterranean Ocean Biogeographic Information System
OBIS	Ocean Biogeographic Information System
SSSA	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies
VEXLUM	Vexlum Ltd
WORMS	World Register of Marine Species
WP	Work Package

MAPWORMS Data Management Questionnaire

Please provide your answers to the following questions considering your Institute/ Organization and the data or/and software which you will create or use during the project life.

For any questions you may have please contact Mrs. Dimitra MAVRAKI, dmavraki@hcmr.gr.

Send us your answers at dmavraki@hcmr.gr and keklikoglou@hcmr.gr by June 24th.

(Please give your answers in detail)

1. Data Summary

What types and formats of data are you going to generate/collect throughout the project?

Will you re-use any existing data and how?

What is the origin of your data?

What is the expected size of the data?

To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

2. FAIR data

Will you keep metadata describing your data? What type of metadata (description, persons involved, protocols etc.)?

Your produced or used data in the project will be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

How will your data be made accessible (e.g., by deposition in a repository, which)?

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

2.3. Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

How you want your data to be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Are you satisfied with CC-BY?

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Are data quality assurance processes described?

Metadata Format for submitted datasets

* *blue*: obligatory metadata field

* *white*: optional metadata field

Dataset title (= A descriptive title is necessary)	
Dataset citation (= Used to cite the dataset in future publications)	
Persons involved (= Define the persons involved and their specific role (indicate contact person))	
Abstract	
Keywords	
Publications (= Publications based on this dataset)	
Usage/ licence (= Specify if the dataset should be made available for public)	
Release date (=if left empty, dataset will immediately be available to the public, otherwise specify the date of release)	
External links (=Dataset already available elsewhere)	

Geographic coverage <i>(= Specify the location)</i>	
Taxonomic coverage <i>(= Specify the main taxonomic groups)</i>	
Funding and acknowledgments	
Equipment used	
Temporal coverage <i>(=First and last date of sampling)</i>	
Area sampled <i>(=Area sampled by equipment)</i>	
Number of stations	
Coordinates	
Number of Replicates <i>(= Per station/sample)</i>	
Habitat description	
Min/max depth	
Biomass present? <i>specify measuring method</i>	
Count present?	
Environ. variables present?	
Additional remarks	

ANNEX IV POTENTIAL (EUROPEAN AND NON-EUROPEAN) DATA REPOSITORIES FOR REDISTRIBUTION OF THE DATA TYPES WITHIN MAPWORMS PROJECT

Thematic data type category	Research domains	Potential data repositories for redistribution	URLs	Comments
Biodiversity data	e.g., biogeographic research, traits, taxonomy	- European Ocean Biogeographic Information System (EurOBIS) - Mediterranean Ocean Biogeographic Information System (MedOBIS) - Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) - Biology Portal of the European Marine Observation and Data Network	http://www.eurobis.org/ http://ipt.medobis.eu/ https://www.gbif.org/ http://www.emodnet.eu/biology	Data availability to OBIS under the following Creative Commons licenses: <u>CC-0</u> <u>CC-BY</u> <u>CC-BY-NC</u> <u>CC BY-SA</u> In addition, shared datasets can be identified and cited through digital object identifiers (DOIs).
Genomic data	DNA Sequencing	- European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) - GenBank - BOLDSYSTEMS	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/ https://www.boldsystems.org/	BOLD shares a tightly integrated data exchange pipeline with NCBI (GenBank) that allows for automatic submission of data to GenBank.
Morphological / Behavioral Data		- Mediterranean Ocean Biogeographic Information System (MedOBIS) - Zenodo	http://ipt.medobis.eu/ https://zenodo.org/	In Zenodo every upload is assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), Regarding license, users must specify it for all publicly available files. Licenses for closed access files may be specified in the description field.
Micro-CT data	e.g. Micro CT images, digital images, videos	-MicroCT vLab	https://microct.portal.ifewatchgreece.eu/	This repository is hosted at the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research which keeps MicroCT vLab active over time through its NOC- Network Operations Center.
Modelling data	e.g. software, codes	- GitHub - Zenodo	https://github.com/ https://zenodo.org/	

Anatomical modelling data		-Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/	
Patent-search data	Evaluation list of prototypes	-Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/	
Experimental data	e.g. publications, graphs	-Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/	
Morphing data		Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/	
Dissemination data	e.g., videos	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/	

ANNEX V DARWIN CORE STANDARDS TERMS FOR BIOGEOGRAPHIC DATA

Darwin_core_term	Definition	Example
occurrenceID	A unique identifier for the occurrence record. This identifier is used to uniquely distinguish a specific occurrence (e.g., an observation or a specimen) from others in a dataset or across datasets.	mapworms:lit:coor:Annelida:1
basisOfRecord	Describes the type of record, such as whether it is an observation, a preserved specimen, or a machine-generated record. Common values include HumanObservation, PreservedSpecimen, FossilSpecimen, MaterialSample, and MachineObservation.	MaterialCitation
eventDate	The date or date range when the event (e.g., observation, collection) occurred. It should be formatted in ISO 8601 (e.g., YYYY-MM-DD).	2016-06-08
originalNameUsage	The original scientific name as it was used in the original source of the data. This can include older taxonomic names or variations that have since changed.	Hermodice carunculata
scientificName	The full scientific name of the organism, typically including genus and species (and sometimes additional taxonomic ranks such as subspecies or variety).	Hermodice carunculata (Pallas, 1766)
kingdom	The highest taxonomic rank of the organism in the biological classification system, representing a major group such as Animalia, Plantae, or Fungi.	Animalia
phylum	The taxonomic rank below kingdom and above class, grouping organisms based on general body plans and shared characteristics (e.g., Chordata for vertebrates).	Annelida
class	A taxonomic rank below phylum and above order, used to group organisms that share common characteristics (e.g., Mammalia for mammals).	Polychaeta
order	A taxonomic rank below class and above family, grouping organisms based on structural features and common ancestry (e.g., Carnivora for carnivorous mammals).	Amphinomida
family	A taxonomic rank below order and above genus, grouping closely related organisms (e.g., Felidae for cats).	Amphinomidae

genus	A taxonomic rank below family and above species, used to group species that are structurally similar or phylogenetically related (e.g., Panthera for big cats like lions and tigers).	Hermodice
specificEpithet	The second part of a binomial scientific name, identifying the species within the genus (e.g., in Homo sapiens, sapiens is the specific epithet).	carunculata
taxonRank	The taxonomic rank of the most specific name in the scientific name, such as species, subspecies, or variety.	species
habitat	The natural environment where the organism was found, describing the setting or type of environment (e.g., forest, desert, marine).	Rock
minimumDepthInMeters	The minimum depth (in meters) at which the organism was found or collected, relevant for aquatic or subterranean species.	60
maximumDepthInMeters	The maximum depth (in meters) at which the organism was found or collected, providing a range for its vertical habitat distribution.	70
decimalLatitude	The latitude of the location where the organism was found, expressed in decimal degrees. Positive values indicate north of the equator.	39,929583
decimalLongitude	The longitude of the location where the organism was found, expressed in decimal degrees. Positive values indicate east of the prime meridian.	18,4055
geodeticDatum	The reference system used for the geographic coordinates, ensuring accurate location data. Common datums include WGS84 and NAD83.	WGS84
country	The name of the country where the organism was found or collected, using the full official name (e.g., United States of America).	Italy
countryCode	The standardized code for the country where the organism was found, typically using ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 format (e.g., US for the United States).	IT
municipality	The name of the municipality or city where the organism was found, providing a more specific location within a country or region.	Tricase
locality	A detailed description of the specific location where the organism was found, often including landmarks, coordinates, or descriptive text.	Torre del Serpe
bibliographicCitation	A reference to a published work related to the occurrence, providing citation details such as authors, title, and publication date.	Micaroni V., et al. (2022) Project "Biodiversity MARE Tricase": A species inventory of the coastal area of Southeastern Salento. Diversity 14: 904.10.3390/d14110904

SAMPLE TYPE ▾ API METADATA ABOUT ▾ OUR APP SEARCH CONTACT

Phascolosoma (*Phascolosoma*) stephensoni

Search Filters

Scientific Name

Sample Type

- Zoology
- Annelida
- Polychaeta
- Eunicida
- Lumbrineridae
- Lumbrineris
- Lumbrineris latreilli
- Eunicidae
- Eunice

Contrast Enhancement Method

- HMDS
- Iodine
- None
- PTA

Project

- BIOIMAGING-GR
- None
- ECCO
- MAPWORMS

Apply

Sample Category : ! Zoology / Annelida

General Info

3D Visualization

Video

Metadata

- Show less metadata

SpecimenID :	! mCT-01334
ScanID :	! scan-01640
Sample Category :	! Zoology / Annelida
Scientific Name :	! <i>Phascolosoma (Phascolosoma) stephensoni</i>
Scientific Name ID :	! https://www.marinespecies.org/aphia.php?p=taxdetails&id=136081
Taxonomic Group :	! ANNELIDA
Provider Institute :	! CONISMA
Project :	! MAPWORMS
Funding :	! European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme
Project Info :	! MAPWORMS project funded from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101046846
Specimen Provider :	! Luigi Musco
Published by :	! Hellenic Centre for Marine Research
Publication Date :	! Thu, 04/04/2024 - 11:30
Material :	! soft tissue
Fixation Type :	! formalin
Preservation Medium :	! Ethanol
Contrast Enhancement Method :	! Iodine
Scope of Scan :	! visualisation of retractor muscles
Scan Date :	! 12/19/2022
Scanned By :	! Niki Keklikoglou
Sample Holder :	! blue pipette tip

[SAMPLE TYPE](#) [API](#) [METADATA](#) [ABOUT](#) [OUR APP](#) [SEARCH](#) [CONTACT](#)

Search Filters

Scientific Name

Sample Type

Zoology
 -Annelida
 --Polychaeta
 ---Eunicida
 ----Lumbrineridae
 -----Lumbrineris
 -----Lumbrineris latreilli
 ----Eunicidae
 -----Eunice

Contrast Enhancement Method

HMDS
 Iodine
 None
 PTA

Project

BIOIMAGING-GR
 None
 ECCO
 MAPWORMS

Apply

Scanning Medium :	ethanol
Scanned Part :	whole specimen
Digital Device Type :	SkyScan 1172
Voltage kV :	50
Current uA :	199
Filter :	None
Zoom um :	6.89
Camera Resolution :	4000
ExposureTime (ms) :	946
360 :	180°
Random Movement :	0
Averaging :	3
Oversize Settings :	None
Dataset :	MAPWORMS_HCMR_scan-01640_v1_20240404.nii_gz (239.29 MB)
Dataset URL :	https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/node/89
Micro-CT Images :	Download MAPWORMS_HCMR_scan-01640image2_v1_20240404.png (393.43 KB) Download MAPWORMS_HCMR_scan-01640image1_v1_20240404.png (551.78 KB)
Video File :	MAPWORMS_HCMR_scan-01640_v1_20240404.mp4 (2.24 MB)
Data Licences :	http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Data Owner :	Niki Keklikoglou
Citation :	Keklikoglou, K., Langeneck, J., Musco, L. (2024). Scan-01640.Micro-CTlab. https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/node/89

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If you use MicroCT_{lab} in a publication, please cite: Keklikoglou K, Faulwetter S, Chatzinikolaou E, Michalakis N, Filiopoulou I, Minadakis N, Panteri E, Perantinos G, Gougousis A, Arvanitidis C (2016) Micro-CT_{lab}: A web based virtual gallery of biological specimens using X-ray microtomography (micro-CT). Biodiversity Data Journal 4: e8740. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.4.e8740>

ANNEX VII PROJECT'S OUTCOMES AND THEIR REPOSITORIES

Partner Contribution	Data Category	Data type	Title	DOI	Repository submitted	Relevant link
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Distributional/ Georeferenced data, Dataset	Georeferenced literature records of annelid species along the Salento Peninsula from 1975 to 2023	https://doi.org/10.15468/xd78ew	a. Zenodo b. MedOBIS c. OBIS d. GBIF	a. https://zenodo.org/records/7869294 b. https://ipt.mediterranean.org/resource?r=georeferenced-literature-annelids-salento-peninsula c. https://obis.org/dataset/68f01f07-36bc-46b9-a57e-ded03db39788 d. https://www.gbif.org/en/dataset/8e6479b6-fb16-493f-8fd6-50f89da374e9
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Distributional data, Dataset	Literature records of annelid species along the Salento Peninsula without georeferenced, 1968-2020	https://doi.org/10.15468/3zz2pj	a. Zenodo b. MedOBIS c. OBIS d. GBIF	a. https://zenodo.org/records/7869960 b. https://ipt.mediterranean.org/resource?r=annelid_salento c. https://obis.org/dataset/8f98c26e-858-484c-86d6-af2860ae87a0 d. https://www.gbif.org/dataset/a47ab2e1-d507-468-b23f-e1cda7739eae
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Distributional/ Georeferenced data, Dataset	New records of annelid species along the Salento Peninsula	https://doi.org/10.25607/zaui2	a. Zenodo b. MedOBIS c. OBIS d. GBIF	a. https://zenodo.org/records/7870065 b. https://ipt.mediterranean.org/resource?r=new_records_annelid_salento c. https://obis.org/dataset/4067c146-db21-4c27-add2-63f85d46109d d. https://www.gbif.org/dataset/77c9cc6c-1c4e-4b08-806d-a95cc4b5829e

CoNISMa	Biological Data	Distributional/ Georeferenced data, Deliverable	D2.1 Georeferenced Annelida distribution map along the Apulia coast	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8039801	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/8039801
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Distributional/ Georeferenced data, poster	Towards a new standard for marine annelid checklists: the Salento Peninsula as a case study	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13897618	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13897618
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Distributional/ Georeferenced data, poster	Biodiversity patterns in marine annelids associated to intertidal coralline algae along the Salento Peninsula	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14185213	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14185213
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Distributional/ Georeferenced data, poster	Marine annelids as models for innovative robots	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8042371	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/8042371
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Genomic data, Dataset	DNA sequencing	dx.doi.org/10.5883/DS-NATPOL25	BOLD Systems	https://portal.boldsystems.org/result?query=MWRM
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Genomic data, Deliverable	D2.3 Integrated molecular/morphological identification of the species	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13897531	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13897531
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Genomic data, Publication	First record of the non-indigenous Myrianida pachycera (Augener, 1913) (Annelida: Syllidae) in the Mediterranean	https://doi.org/10.3391/bir.2025.14.3.16	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18661501

			Sea revealed by integrative taxonomy			
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Genomic data, Publication	Bridging past and present: the Salento Peninsula as a case study for unveiling marine annelid diversity by integrating literature, field surveys, and DNA barcoding	https://doi.org/10.1080/24750263.2026.2614131	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18661322
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Genomic data, Publication	Non-indigenous polychaetes along the Salento Peninsula: new records and first molecular data	https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.35851	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13843469
HCMR	Biological Data	Morphological and behavioral data, Dataset	Micro-CT Morphological Data of Glycera tridactyla Schmarda, 1861 and Phascolosoma (Phascolosoma) stephensoni (Stephen, 1942) species	https://doi.org/10.25607/mq-d09f	a. MedOBIS b. OBIS c. GBIF	a. https://ipt.medobis.eu/resource?r=micro-ct_morphological_data_glycera-tridactyla-phascolosoma-stephensoni b. https://obis.org/dataset/74cc1af5-06e8-4c7e-9e87-0a862b9af5a9 c. https://www.gbif.org/dataset/22fa3c39-2ff0-4f78-826f-bf526df17354
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Morphological and behavioral data, Deliverable	D2.2 First set of parameters for modelling	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13897604	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13897604
CoNISMa	Biological Data	Morphological and behavioral data, Deliverable	D2.4 Annelida performance final characterization	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18661112	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18661112

HCMR	Biological Data	Micro CT data, image data	MAPWORMS collection		a. MicroCTvlab b. Mobile web application	a. https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/ b. https://microctapp.hcmr.gr/
HCMR	Biological Data	Micro CT data, protocols	MAPWORMS Micro-CT imaging protocols	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14039803	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14039803
SSSA	Technical Data	Modelling data, Deliverable	D3.1 Validated morphing algorithm for smart hydrogels based on non-euclidean plates	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14199334	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14199334
SSSA	Technical Data	Modelling data, Deliverable	D3.2 Validated direct morphing FEM algorithms	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14199377	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14199377
SSSA	Technical Data	Modelling data, Deliverable	D3.3 Morphing of structures: inverse IBV problem	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18846589	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18846589
SSSA	Technical Data	Modelling data, poster	Modeling McKibben artificial muscles through differential geometry	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8028524	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/8028524
SSSA	Technical Data	Modelling data, Dataset	Mechanical characterization of agar gel	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19091582	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/19091582
SSSA	Technical Data	Modelling data, Dataset	2D COMSOL simulation of magnetic bender	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19090617	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/19090617
VEXLUM	Technical Data	Laser characterization data, Deliverable	D5.3 Laser system for light stimulation	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18846117	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18846117

VEXLUM	Technical Data	Laser characterization data, Datasheet	VEXLUM, laser characterisation report	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13939007	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13939007
VEXLUM	Technical Data	Laser characterization data, presentation	Progress of turnkey VECSEL systems for quantum technology	https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2656414	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/8046794
HUJI	Technical Data	Experimental Data, Deliverable	D4.1 - Delivery of available smart responsive hydrogels for preliminary modelling and for devising integration possibilities	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8041622	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/8041622
HUJI	Technical Data	Experimental Data, Deliverable	D4.2 - Immobilized stimuli-responsive hydrogels on surfaces	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14199396	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14199396
HUJI	Technical Data	Experimental Data, Deliverable	D4.3 Synthesis and characterisation of shape-memory and self-healing hydrogels	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18648239	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18648239
HUJI	Technical Data	Experimental Data, Deliverable	D4.4 Immobilized stimuli-responsive hydrogels on surfaces - update	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18648369	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18648369
HUJI	Technical Data	Experimental Data, publication	Chemical and Photochemical-Driven Dissipative Fe ³⁺ /Fe ²⁺ -Ion Cross-Linked Carboxymethyl Cellulose Gels Operating Under Aerobic	https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.4c00625?urlapend=%3Fref%3DPDF&jav=VOR&rel=cite-as	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/10980500

			Conditions: Applications for Transient Controlled Release and Mechanical Actuation			
HUJI	Technical Data	Experimental Data, publication	Stiffness- Switchable, Biocatalytic pH- Responsive DNA- Functionalized Polyacrylamide Cryogels and their Mechanical Applications	https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202306586	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/10980339
HUJI	Technical Data	Experimental Data, publication and supporting material (raw data)	Stimuli-Responsive DNA-Based Hydrogels on Surfaces for Switchable Bioelectrocatalysis and Controlled Release of Loads	https://doi.org/10.1021/acscami.3c06230	Zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19119159
ACMIT	Technical Data	Data Sheet	Brain phantom data sheet	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19733305	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/19733305
SSSA	Technical Data	Morphing Data, Deliverable	D5.1 - First working actuation unit	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14199421	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14199421
SSSA	Technical Data	Morphing Data, Deliverable	D5.2 - First version of actuation units combination	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14199474	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14199474
SSSA	Technical Data	Morphing data, Poster	Worm-Inspired Soft Robot with Magnetically Driven Eversible Proboscis	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18219665	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18219665

SSSA	Technical Data	Morphing raw data	Magnetically-Driven Deployable Structure Inspired by Worms	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18221609	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18221609
SSSA	Technical Data	Morphing data, Poster	Mimicking Adaptation and Plasticity in WORMS: the MAPWORMS Project	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7912991	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/7912991
SSSA	Technical Data	Morphing data, Publication	A Bioinspired Fluid-Filled Soft Linear Actuator	https://doi.org/10.1089/soro.2021.0091	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/7866839
SSSA	Technical Data	Morphing data, Publication and raw data	Unsegmented marine annelids as biomechanical models for soft robotics	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-026-44047-w	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/19088049
SSSA	Technical Data	Morphing data, poster	Reconfigurable Soft Magnetic Architectures for Deployable Morphing Structures	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19387862	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/19387862
ACMIT	Technical Data	Patent-search Data, Deliverable	D6.1 - Preliminary IP report	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8041663	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/8041663
ACMIT	Technical Data	Patent-search Data, Deliverable	D6.2 - Report on task primitives' definition and self-healing hydrogels	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14199540	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14199540
ACMIT	Technical Data	Patent-search Data, Deliverable	D6.3 Final IP Report	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18936934	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/18936934

All	Dissemination Data	video	MAPWORMS - Mimicking Adaptation and Plasticity in WORMS	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14246963	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14246963
All	Dissemination Data	video	PROJECT'S OVERVIEW VIDEO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13939616	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13939616
SSSA	Dissemination Data	deliverable	D1.1 - Website and Project LOGO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13906912	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13906912
SSSA	Dissemination Data	deliverable	D1.4 - Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8039651	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/8039651
SSSA	Dissemination Data	deliverable	D1.5 - Annual report on key communication events	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13906885	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13906885
SSSA	Dissemination Data	deliverable	D1.8 - Report on Key Communication Events - 2nd Reporting Period	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14199272	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/14199272
HCMR	Dissemination Data	poster	Scientific community needs: FAIR and credible data repositories. The case of MedOBIS Repository and MAPWORMS Project	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13827761	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13827761
HCMR	Dissemination Data	presentation	Applying FAIR principles to Micro-CT data, the case of MAPWORMS PROJECT	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13683253	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13683253
SSSA	Dissemination Data	video	Video presenting 3D printing	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13939664	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/13939664
HCMR SSSA	Dissemination Data	poster	poster (in Greek) presented at the "Crete and Sea" event, organized by HCMR and FORTH, Crete, Greece	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19230960	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/19230960

